

Gender Discrimination at Work Place: A Case Study on Education Sector of Pakistan

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Abstract

The paper explores the existence of the gender discrimination at work place in education sector of Pakistan and how work place environment effects the gender discrimination. Gender discrimination is a fact of our culture but it's varying from society to society in Pakistan. To determine the factor of the gender discrimination, semi structured interview has been used for data collection. Nvivo software has been used to transcribe the data and identify the themes through thematic analysis. However, results indicated that politics found in every department of the organizations whether it's public or private but did not find more discrimination. It's found up to some extent in the education sector. Basically this study indicated that in this globalization era women are not discriminated at work places.

Key words: gender discrimination, work place, culture.

1) Introduction

Gender discrimination is a fact in our society but it varies from society to society in Pakistani culture (Delavande & Zafar, 2013) according to Economic Survey Report of Pakistan 2012 literacy rate of girls is 22% which is compared to 47% boys. Majority in backward area of Pakistan women have not played the role in the income. Families did not like the women to earn, all these people belongs to the illiterate families. The effect of public sector for women discrimination is more as compared to the private sector. Post group of the education women face more discrimination as compared to the men (Channer,2010). According to Muslim book of HOLY Quran gives equal rights to men and women with their rights and responsibilities. Majority of the study has been conducted in western context or used by the quantitative approach. This study will be completely designed on qualitative approach by findings the research gap from the literature. However, employee is the asset of the organization and in developing countries it is important to treat equally on the basis of the education and skill.

It is found that Human resource management is playing vital role in any organization and creates distinction from other organization and deals with the people dimension (john, 2004). Human resource management have concerned to hire and develop the skills of the employees and retain them. There are two types of the discrimination fair and unfair discrimination. Fair discrimination is based on the skill capabilities and their individual differences however unfair discrimination defines as to discriminate the employee on the basis of sex, color, cast etc. In 1950's and 1960's there existed similarity in homogeneous work place. According to the federal legislation in 1960's it was prohibited to employee discrimination (David et al., 2004).

In Era of globalization creates the diversity which established the heterogeneous work place to perform the employee according to the specialized area in the organization (wayne, 1995). Managing diversity is a tool which is creates the equal employment opportunity. Equal employee opportunity EEO is an amendment which is passed by the congress in 1972 prohibited to discrimination at workplace on the basis of gender race color sect and religion. Islam emphasizes on the merit system rather than other system however in western countries they followed the merit system. In recruitment and selection processes has been followed the equal employment opportunity legislation. According to the Wayne (1992) equal employment opportunity indicates two things which includes that to evaluate the employees according to their achievement and secondly to how to deal with employees on the basis of the equality. Discrimination of the men and women in economic and social role has increased the poverty of women in the society (Muqadissa, 2004). Salwa (1988) has stated that there is no term of discrimination but the context of the employment has defined as giving fair or unfair advantages. Gender difference on the basis of social role and status in the society is called gender discrimination (Anderson,

1998).the people who are working in good environment exert more effort. Therefore, the aim of this study is to analyze the effect of working environment on gender discrimination.

1.1.Research question:

1. Does gender discrimination exist at work place in education sector of Pakistan?
2. How does environment of work place effect the gender discrimination?

1.2.Purpose of the study:

The aim of the study is to explore the existence of gender discrimination at work place in education sector of Pakistan. Mostly previous research was conducted on gender discrimination by using the quantitative research method. This study relies on the education staff members to examine the work place culture of the organization. Qualitative research has been used for this research and data collected through semi structured interview.

1.3.Significance of the study:

The present study will be significant in the following way:

This study will help us to find out the major causes at work place in the education sector of Pakistan because majority of the study was conducted in the western context and using the quantitative research methodology. This study analyses the major causes which arise the gender discrimination at work place. In this research we have used the qualitative research method, this research contributed in the body of literature as a qualitative research perspective. It will help HEC (Higher education commission of Pakistan) to amend their policies and to focus more on the quality standard of education by recommending this sector about improvement in their human resource practice.

2) Literature Review

2.1. Traditional differences

Gender discrimination means discrepancy between human beings on the basis of the gender. Gender difference falls in the society in many different ways which included the social or traditional perceptions and biological differences. Cultural and traditional differences discussed about the perception of the society aspects depend upon the status which are described in the society. On the other hand the biological differences define the chromo somatic differences genetically but Islam treats the humanity on the basis of equality. Mainly in societies women are behaved as a minority, measured through status and take benefits from wages, laws etc. (Jacobs, Jerry 1995).Due to increase in the society women become subordinate to the men (Harris, 1980 and Leacock, 1978). Alma (2011) stated that mostly women totally depend on the men reason behind the low income due to sex segregation. Women have not availed the equal opportunities in different department except teaching in government sector. In our society old tradition effect have negatively impact on the poverty elevation.

2.2. Status of women in Pakistan:

According to the Pakistani surveys report (2008-9) 2/3 population is living in the rural area. Per anum growth rate of women is greater than men 2.6, 2.5 respectively. Through training and monitoring it's a process for women to generate as a political representative and 20 % quota reserved for women in the government of Pakistan and India. (Chris 2004). After the foundation of Pakistan women's spend their life with freedom and equality with men as compared to previous time but traditional thinking of some people yet not change (Azra, 2004). According to the area of the country we have seen different diversity in women status in rural urban

society's communities. A mostly woman's working in a low paid salary jobs with limited career opportunities' (shah et al., 2004).

2.3. Access to education:

According to the Islam the prophet Muhammad (SAW) of Allah said,

“Acquiring knowledge is compulsory for every Muslim” (Tirmizi Hadith: 74,107)

The narration of the hadith in the context of knowledge it's compulsory for men and women equally. Women have equal right to acquire knowledge in her life. The culture of the Pakistan contains that parents invest on their daughter education, practices are not possible due to unemployment and women migrate to their husband home and do not receive any rate of return on their education (shah et al., 2004). According to shah et al., (2004) 29% women are illiterate in the village 3% women's are educated at primary level and 0.9% at matriculation level. Participatory development and gender participation in decision making researches shows that 15.1 %, 16.6%, 15.9%, 41.1% and 2.9% women are independent in house decision, family participation, and health related, matrimonial respectively. In 1998 the World Bank mentioned the four points for women welfare. First is ratio of death rate of the gender secondly human resource development in education and welfare third is the growth rate of the population and last point is the contribution of the women in the economy (WB, 1998).

2.4. Gender discrimination in NWFP and Baluchistan:

Gender discrimination exists all over the world while In Pakistan the higher ratio has fallen on the rural areas and particularly in the provinces of NWFP and Baluchistan. Gender discrimination always exists in the household life like marriages education wealth and in the economic field of women lifelike per hour salary which is comparable to the men. Women have no rights in the property which is received from father brother. Through education we get better employment but there are many hurdles in women's life to get higher education, man enjoys the good designation and salary and women get only secondary jobs like assistant. In NWFP and Baluchistan negative point of view regarding working women is, male are dominating and give priority to the “parda” (Amnesty International, 1995).

2.5. Women at work place:

In 1990 13% women's were working as a labor work force but from 2005 to 2009 contribution of female has increased up to 33% and 67% to men. According to the human resource development index 2008, Pakistan rank falling is 144 in out of 175 countries but according to human development index the rank of Pakistan is 120.

2.6. Approaches

According to the (women in development approach) women play productive role in the development phase of the society and they fulfill the strategic needs with direct state invention, as soon this approached is replaced by the anti-property approach. Due to the strategic needs equity and empowerment has been labeled by the gender and development) GAD (Alam, 2011). Rational base theory according to this theory, policy makers have decided to discriminate on the basis of superiority and inferiority on their career aspects.in business oriented organization women are more discriminated from management side. Earlier researches reflect that equal opportunities increase gender discrimination due to the external pressure than internal pressure. (Susan et al., 1998)

In Bangladesh glass ceiling effect studied that research predicts that women are discriminated from higher post to lower post. Government policies are proving to be ineffective because there is no discrimination for upper class ladies (Habib , 2000). Uzma (2004) stated that there is two point of view of our society which includes how

people perceive you and how you perceive the society. Parents behavior towards the children create the identity however, educational women have double identity, professional and personal.

2.6.1. Dyadic power:

In previous literature there are different power discussed like dyadic power and structural power. Dyadic power means to the excess ratio of one gender in the society and other gender may influences on majority of the gender (Alma, 2011)

2.6.2. Structural power

Excess number of women always creates social group in the society according to the old tradition. We have the point of view that women will be more influential and powerful in coming periods. There are different reasons behind the women poverty at different stages in the community. At general stage in society we have seen the institutional discrimination and at community stage social responsibilities affect men and women at house hold level and unequal power in relation (Nilufer, 1998).

McNamara's stated the report stated at World Bank in 1973, poverty means have "no capability" due to following reasons like low income lack of education and accommodation services. Women are discriminated in Sweden through glass ceiling effect and they suffer more due to like environment. (Erik et al., 2006)

2.6.3. Equal employment opportunity:

EEO is a broad concept. According to the Wayne (1995) equal employment opportunities' are focuses on the equal employment chance to each employee. It helps the employee to achieve the organization goal. Affirmative action defines as to remove the barriers of the EEO. In which organizations use the affirmative action they hide the discrimination and represent the minorities of the organization. (Raymond et al., 2004)

According to the universal declaration of human rights article state 2 *"Everyone is entitled to all rights and freedom set forth in this connection without distinction of any kind, such as race, color, sex, language, religious, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status"* (UN, 1948)

In Norway iceland and France have set the supervisory body to investigate the complaints from research under law of gender equality. Supervisory bodies are responsible for any negligence in the legislation of discrimination. International standards provide the equality to women against the discrimination.

Basically gender discrimination is not a problem of the legislation of the country. It is a mind problem attitude of the peoples which creates discrimination. It is a mindset that women are not capable to hold the social responsibilities. Mostly women's play multitasks in the society, job house responsibilities.

2.7. Research Gap:

Research finds out the impact of the gender discrimination on gender development in higher education commission (Salik & Zhiyong, 2014). Present research deals with the gender discrimination at work place from public and private organizations.

2.8. Research Question:

1. Does gender discrimination exist at work place in education sector of Pakistan?
2. How does environment of work place effect the gender discrimination?

3) RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Non probability sampling is following in qualitative research. Convenience sampling has been used for data collection. Sampling size based on which discussed in previous research and also described by the (Bryman and

Bell, 2009). Ten members were selected from education sector that have experience more than 2 years at work place. Data has been collected equally from the males and females in education sector of the Pakistan. Instrument of data collection is semi structured interview that has been used to analyses the effect of working environment on gender discrimination and adapted the interview protocol for interview.

3.1. Data analysis strategy: Transcription of the data has showed the findings and results of the data which is related to the research problem. NIVVO software has been used to interpret the themes which are discussed in the open ended questionnaire

3.2. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:

The ethical issue will be kept under consideration during research work.

- The purpose of study is made too clear and simple for reader and respondents.
- Collected information from the respondents will be secured from any harmful consequences.
- Mutual consent was important part of the data collection in my research work.
- Determining the problem statement has been ensured that research would benefit the individuals.

4) Analysis of the findings

The objective of analysis is to facilitate the reader to interact with the multiple realities which has been found through data analysis. Table 01 provides the demographics of the sample selected for qualitative study. Context of the research shows the experience of gender discrimination at work place. In appendix 1 mention the word query of the gender discrimination and in appendix 2 shows the text search query.

Table 01 DEMOGRAPHICS PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Sr.No	Interviewee	Qualification	experiences	Sector	Teaching/non-Teaching staff
1	Participants(P1)	M.Phil.	8 years	Public	Teaching
2	P2	M.Phil.	5 years	Private	Teaching
3	P3	M.A	15 years	Public	Teaching
4	P4	M.Phil.	3 years	Public	Teaching
5	P5	M.Phil.	7 years	Private	Non-teaching
6	P6	M.A	6 years	Public	Non-teaching
7	P7	PhD	20 years	Public	Teaching
8	P8	M.Phil.	5 years	Private	Teaching
9	P9	M.sc	17 years	Public	Teaching
10	P10	M.Phil.	7 years	Private	Teaching

Thematic Analysis:

After transcribing the data, themes are identified from qualitative data. Thematic analysis has been used for data analyses and to identify the main themes whom to be answered the research question. The data are transcribed

which consist of the teaching and non-teaching staff qualitative interview which are collected from the respondents of the education departments findings, based upon the following themes 1)culture of the work place 2)problem at work place 3)favoritism and stress 4)Recruitment criteria 5)public and private sector.

Table 02 Matrix coding query

Participants	Culture at work place	problem at work place	public and private sector	Recruitment criteria	Stress and favoritism
P1	1	1	1	2	2
P2	1	1	1	2	2
P3	1	1	0	2	3
P4	1	1	1	2	2
P5	1	1	1	2	2
P6	1	1	1	3	2
P7	1	1	1	2	2
P8	1	1	1	2	2
P9	1	1	1	2	2
P10	1	1	1	2	2

Explanation:

By using the Nvivo software matrix coding queries are indicating the following result which shows the word frequency in transcribed data. Table 02 shows the 4 themes moreover, the recruitment criteria, Stress and favoritism have more impact on gender discrimination at workplace and promote the deception at work place. According to the data the culture at work place and problems at work place have impact but not greater than to the recruitment criteria, stress and favouritism. In any organization whether it’s public or private have a recruitment strategy which indicates the preference towards education and gender. Due to opposite gender organizations faces the problems like stress and favoritism. All these cause the retention of the employees and they switch off the job.

Table 03 Summary of findings on gender discrimination at work place

Research question	Themes	Category
How environment of work place effects on the gender discrimination?	culture of the work place	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Rules and regulation of the organization. ✓ Difficult situation. ✓ Promotion policy. ✓ Flexibility and control of management.
	Problem at work place	
	Favoritism and stress	
Does gender discrimination exist at work place in education sector of Pakistan?	Recruitment criteria/ less pay scale	Importance of the merit Deals according to the capability
	public sector and private sector	

The aim of table 03 to analyze the data and has been collected from the respondent who work in the educational department and have their experience at work place in different situations .secondly it helps to understand the environment of the department which effects the discrimination, if department play a role as a team's importance and establish the human resource management practices then they will prohibit the discrimination.

RESEARCH MODEL

Explanation

Nvivo software produced the model after data analysis. This model depicts the factors which effected the gender discrimination. Public and private sector have impact on gender discrimination it's a one way relationship. Problem at work places indicated the mutual relationship with gender discrimination at work place. Recruitment and selections have an impact on the gender discrimination and it is associated with the public and private sector. Both sectors have different rules and discipline. That's why they are associated with each other and impact on the gender discrimination. Stress and favoritism indicated the mutual relationship with gender discrimination because favoritisms promotes the discrimination at work place and that's why stress increases mostly in females at work place.

5.3. CONCLUSION

Research indicated the women status in the society, according to the tradition/ culture, women were discriminated and subordinate to the men. Due to education and in Islam women have equal rights as men in the society. On the basis of the qualitative findings in education sector, there is no more discrimination in education sector employees are co-operative with each other and recruitment selection based upon the merit and capabilities of the employees. Results indicated that politics found everywhere and discrimination prevails more in private sector than in public sector.

5.4. Recommendation and implication of the theory:

It's a recommendation to provide the equal employments opportunities and education to each employee according to their needs. To provide the same and defined promotion policy and selection procedure are for each employee. To provide the equal opportunities the each candidate to participate in the activities this helped the organization to remove the conflicts and discrimination at work place.

This study should be implies in the education sector because it's a qualitative study and conducted from education sector the results will not be generalized. This research is contributed to the qualitative study in the context of the Pakistan and also it's helpful for policy makers to provide the positive environment to their employees and amend their policies to remove the element of the discrimination at work place.

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Appendices 1

Appendices 2

